

Concerted European action on Sustainable Applications of REfractories

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Project Coordinator: **Marc HUGER**, marc.huger@unilim.fr, IRCER

www.cesaref.eu

Deliverable D5.1 - CESAREF eLearning Tool

Primary authors:

Simon ETZOLD, Elsa THUNE, Thorsten TONNESEN

Document contributors:

Marc HUGER, Glyn DERRICK

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History of Changes for this Deliverable

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1 Introduction

CESAREF will deliver a customisable training approach for each PhD candidate, supported by FIRE. The diversity of the thematic aspects of the scientific topics covered within CESAREF and the valuable experience gained from the organisation of training sessions within the previous ATHOR project (www.etn-athor.eu) prompt us to organise a more individual approach. This will maximise the benefit of the organised training actions. Based on the respective research focus, the PhD candidates will benefit from opportunities for thematic specialisation and exchange with experts. The network will provide webinars, recorded lectures, scientific/technical literature reviews. This approach allows efficient integration into the individual schedules, provides in-depth learning success, while saving travel time and protecting the environment (see <https://marie-sklodowska-curie-actions.ec.europa.eu/about-msca/msca-green-charter>).

To share content for educational use within CESAREF, RWTH hosts a virtual learning platform for the PhD students and all involved partner companies and universities. This eLearning portal will give access to presentations, literature as well as recorded lectures and webinars on the multifaceted topics of the CESAREF project.

2 Host and accessibility

The virtual classroom of the CESAREF project, “ELEANOR” (Electronic LEARNING Network On Refractories), will be administrated by RWTH Aachen University within the runtime of the CESAREF project (**Figure 1**). Not only CESAREF PhD students and project partners will be enabled to access the available content, also refractory students at the participating universities and scientists/engineers of the partner companies may request login details for external users.

The eLearning platform used for this purpose, “RWTHmoodle” (a university-based spin-off of the original Moodle with the same functionality) is hosted by RWTH Aachen University. This platform provides free, virtually unlimited storage space which allows the eLearning content to grow while CESAREF Training Events are taking place.

As a free and open-source learning management system (LMS) distributed under the GNU General Public License, Moodle meets the requirements within the CESAREF project. Developed on pedagogical principles, the fields of application are different eLearning concepts, e. g. blended learning, distance education and flipped classrooms, in schools, universities, companies and other sectors all over the world.

The functionality of Moodle surpasses common learning environments and exhibits a wide range of standard and innovative features such as calendar, gradebook, discussion forum and support of mobile devices via App.

Figure 1: Example of access to eLearning environment ELEANOR

3 Public content

A considerable amount of the provided content will be recordings of CESAREF training events and webinars, virtual presentations held at regular intervals (presumably every 4-6 weeks). Especially valuable for highly detailed topics, CESAREF's expertise is transferred without excluding any party. These webinars will be recorded and published, with permission, on the eLearning platform. All CESAREF partners are encouraged to provide virtual lectures on their area of expertise, which led to an enormous amount of knowledge exchange in previous collaborations, e. g. *ETN ATHOR*.

Webinars will partly replace courses of the **Research Training Courses (RTCs)** and **Complementary Skills Workshops (CSWs)** to reduce travelling, and add more scientific depth, as the face-to-face courses intend to reach all participants from different thematic backgrounds equally.

Further content, e. g. literature, presentation slides or video files showing experiments or laboratory equipment, to contribute to an in-depth training of the consortium members in certain topics can also be added by the consortium members and will lead to an ever-expanding eLearning environment during the CESAREF project lifespan. This approach also makes it possible to consider thematic fields representing niche areas in the overall context of the project.

4 Subsequent use

After the lifespan of the CESAREF project, the Steering Board and all contributing partners will decide about the subsequent use of the gathered content within the Federation for International Refractory Research and Education (FIRE). The terms of use and the publication of gathered contents will be approached separately from the CESAREF context after the project period and will be discussed with the involved parties prior to the performance of further steps but the work package leader considers a subsequent use of ELEANOR as a service for all partners of the FIRE consortium which is already considered in the logo (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Logo of ELEANOR platform

5 Conclusions

The CESAREF eLearning platform ELEANOR is a virtual classroom enabling the transfer of knowledge, communication and exchange within the framework of the project. It will be regularly updated and improved by project members (contributing partners, PhD students and the administration team of RWTH Aachen University) in order to provide a beneficial eLearning environment. The subsequent use of the gathered content is considered within the FIRE consortium.

The webspace provided by the RWTH Aachen University (RWTHmoodle) is meeting the project needs in terms of hosting of the gathered data, accessibility via mobile devices and offering administrative support.

This Deliverable D5.1 is living a document which will be thus updated every 12 months.